

Support:

Post Graduate
Functional and Molecular Biology

A Crazy Dream

Starring: Insulin

PRESENTATION

This resource was developed by graduate students of the Functional and Molecular Biology program from the Biology Institute of Unicamp, in the course “Molecular Basis of Gene Expression”, taught by Professor Carmen Veríssima Ferreira-Halder. At first we were challenged to develop teaching and dissemination resource related to Molecular Biology to provide to undergraduate students. After a discussion among our group the idea of drawing up a comic book emerged. It was a great challenge to relate gene expression to a didactic story that could be presented in a comic book and another one was to decide among the topics which could be addressed. We decided to talk about insulin, since it is responsible for regulating gene transcription of over a hundred proteins essential for cell cycle and homeostasis. Thus, we expect that with this auxiliar resource, undergraduate students will understand the correlation between gene expression and cellular metabolism related to a signaling pathway triggered by insulin.

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Reinforcing key concepts

Down

- 1- SREBP is a transcription factor that stimulates transcription of genes that encode proteins related to...
- 2- The binding of insulin to its receptor occurs in the... environment.
- 3- The requisite for SREBP-1c transportation by COP2 carrier is low concentration of... in the cell.
- 4- The one which interacts with sterol regulatory elements in the DNA is...
- 5- mTOR verifies the nutritional conditions of the cell to stimulate...

Across

- 6- The binding of insulin to its receptor leads to ... of that receptor.
- 7- mTOR is activated by ...
- 8- AKT is a ..., or a protein that is able to phosphorylate other proteins.

Answers: 1- Lipogenesis, 2- Extracellular, 3- Sterol, 4- bHLH, 5- Gene expression, 6- Autophosphorylation, 7- RHEB, 8- Kinase

Hi Anne, how is it going?

You won't believe what I have to tell you. Last night I had the craziest dream after our molecular biology class.

I dreamed of the signaling pathway of gene expression of proteins related to lipogenesis which is regulated by insulin binding to its receptor... Do you remember the class we had yesterday?! Now I think I understood better how this cellular mechanism works.

Wow, really?! So tell me about your dream, because I didn't understand that part of the lesson so well. I was kind of confused. Insulin pathway is so complex. It has so many important functions in our body!

Yeah Anne. My dream helped me understand part of its complexity.

(PETER) IN FACT, I DREAMED WITH THE INSULIN BOUND TO THE EXTRACELLULAR SUBUNIT OF ITS RECEPTOR (IR)....

(PETER) THIS BINDING OF INSULIN TO THE EXTRACELLULAR SUBUNIT ALTERED THE INTRACELLULAR SUBUNIT OF ITS RECEPTOR LEADING TO SELF-PHOSPHORYLATION. THEN, THIS INSULIN RECEPTOR (IR) SELF-PHOSPHORYLATION (P) AROUSED THE INSULIN RECEPTOR SUBSTRATE (IRS-1), WHICH SEEMED TO BE ASLEEP IN THE CYTOPLASM AND SUDDENLY AWOKE.

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(PETER) RIGHT AFTER NOTICING THAT THE IRS-1 WAS AWAKE AND INTERACTING WITH CELL MEMBRANE PROTEINS, CHARMING AND ATTRACTIVE PI3K, AS USUAL, FELT ATTRACTED BY IRS-1, USING ALL HER CHARM TO GET CLOSE.

(PETER) REALIZING WHAT WAS OCCURRING BETWEEN IRS-1 AND PI3K AT THE CELL MEMBRANE, AKT ALSO MOVED THERE TO INTERACT WITH PI3K;

(PETER) AFTER THE APPROACH AND INTERACTION BETWEEN AKT AND PI3K, AKT REALIZED SHE HAD TO GO TO THE TSC1/TSC2 COMPLEX TO STOP THEIR INFLUENCE OVER RHEB.

PETER HOW COULD YOU HAVE SUCH A DREAM? I'VE NEVER SEEN ANYTHING LIKE IT BEFORE!

IT WAS TRIPPY, WASN'T IT ANNE?! I GUESS I STUDIED SIGNALING PATHWAYS TOO MUCH, LOOKING FOR A WAY TO UNDERSTAND THE ROLE OF EACH PROTEIN, ITS IMPORTANCE AND FUNCTION THAT I EVEN DREAMT ABOUT THEM.

YOUR DREAM HELPED ME IMPROVE MY UNDERSTANDING ABOUT THE IMPORTANCE OF INSULIN IN THE ACTIVATION OF mTOR, WHICH IS THE PROTEIN THAT IDENTIFIES IF THE NUTRITIONAL STATE OF THE CELL IS SUITABLE FOR PROTEIN SYNTHESIS TO OCCUR. A POSITIVE RESULT LEADS TO SIGNALING TO SREBP-1c PROTEIN, SO IT IS TRANSLOCATED TO THE NUCLEUS AS bHLH DOMAIN. THERE, IT WILL HAVE AN ESSENTIAL ROLE IN THE GENE EXPRESSION THAT WILL GENERATE PROTEINS RESPONSIBLE FOR LIPOGENESIS.

I WISH I ALSO HAD THAT KIND OF DREAM! HAHA.

END

(PETER) DUE TO THE INHIBITION OF TSC1/TSC2 COMPLEX BY AKT, THROUGH PHOSPHORYLATION, RHEB WAS NOW FREE TO ACT, SO IT WENT TO THE IMPORTANT mTOR TO LET HIM KNOW THAT HE COULD NOW FOLLOW UP HIS MAIN FUNCTIONS IN THE NUCLEUS...

THE IMPORTANCE OF LIPOGENESIS REGULATED BY SREBP-1c

Indirectly activated by insulin, SREBP-1c will perform an important role in the expression of approximately 30 genes that are involved in synthesis and uptake of cholesterol, fatty acids, triglycerides and phospholipids. In the liver, SREBP-1c regulates the synthesis of lipids increasing, preferably, transcription of the gene responsible for the enzyme acetyl CoA carboxylase, which catalyzes the conversion of acetyl CoA to malonyl CoA, a precursor in the synthesis of fatty acids. In the biosynthesis of cholesterol, SREBP-1c regulates the production of the enzyme HMG-CoA reductase, responsible for the formation of cholesterol. Finally, SREBP-1c also regulates the secretion of acetyl-CoA synthetase, activating enzyme of acetate for the synthesis of lipids and energy generation.

(PETER) DURING THE PARTY AT NUCLEUS' BAR, bHLH UNDERSTOOD WHY HE WAS THE GUEST OF HONOR. HE FELT A STRONG ATTRACTION FOR THE DNA STEROL RESPONSE DOMAINS (SRE) THAT WAS PRESENT AT NUCLEUS' BAR.

(PETER) THROUGH THIS STRONG INTERACTION BETWEEN THEM, NEW PROTEINS WERE TRANSLATED THAT PLAYED AN IMPORTANT ROLE IN THE LIPOGENESIS PATHWAY.

(PETER) AT THAT TIME, ANNE, mTOR WENT ON TO CHECK THE AVAILABILITY OF AMINO ACIDS AND ENERGY IN THE CELL. AFTER REALIZING THAT BOTH NUTRITIONAL AND ENERGETIC CONDITIONS WERE APPROPRIATE HE CONCLUDED IT WOULD BE POSSIBLE TO PROMOTE A BIG PARTY AT NUCLEUS' BAR. THEN, mTOR BEGAN THE PREPARATIONS FOR THE PARTY.

(PETER) SO mTOR, AS THE PARTY ORGANIZER, RESPONSIBLE FOR PROMOTING AND ORGANIZING THE GUEST LIST, INVITED SREBP-1c TELLING HIM THAT HIS PRESENCE WAS FUNDAMENTAL, AND THAT HE WOULD HAVE A KEY ROLE IN THIS PARTY, WHICH HE WOULD UNDERSTAND WHEN HE CAME TO NUCLEUS' BAR.

PETER, WHAT AN AMAZING DREAM!!!! GO ON, I'M CURIOUS TO KNOW THE END TO THIS STORY...

(PETER) STILL IN MY DREAM, SREBP-1c WAS AT A BUS STOP NAMED ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM, TIED TO SCAP, WHO WAS CHAINED TO INSIG WAITING FOR THE COP2 BUS LINE. HOWEVER, SO THAT SREBP-1c AND SCAP COULD BOARD THE BUS, IT WOULD BE NECESSARY THAT THE CELL HAD A LOW LEVEL OF STEROL.

(PETER) SINCE THE STEROL CONCENTRATION WAS LOW, SO THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SCAP AND INSIG WAS UNDONE, AND SREBP-1c AND SCAP COULD TRAVEL WITH THE COP2 LINE.

(PETER) BEFORE GETTING TO THE PARTY, SCAP AND SREBP-1c HAD TO MAKE A STOP IN THE GOLGI COMPLEX TERMINAL.... AFTER A SINCERE CONVERSATION, SCAP REALIZED THAT SHE WAS "BOTHERING" SREBP-1c AND GAVE UP GOING TO THE PARTY.

(PETER) THEN, ALONE, SREBP-1c BECAME bHLH DOMAIN, AND BOARDED THE IMPORTIN beta BUS TOWARD THE PARTY.

